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Urban Poverty in Malaysia: A Bibliometric Analysis

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received: 2 June 2023 Revised: 25 June 2023 Accepted: 7 August 2023 Published: 1 September 2023</p> <p>Keywords: Bibliometric Urban Poverty Malaysia Scopus database</p>	<p>By conducting a bibliometric analysis of 5,419 papers from the Scopus database between 2019 and 2023, this study intends to completely evaluate the urban poverty research field. The study aims to identify the most significant authors, universities, countries, and citations in the field, to highlight author, university, and country collaborations in the field, to learn about the research topics that researchers have been working on recently, and to look at Malaysia's contribution to the field. According to the research, Malaysia, China, and the United States are the top three in terms of reducing urban poverty. The most well-known author is Zaman, K., and the host universities for urban poverty researchers are mostly Universiti Sains Malaysia, Universiti Malaya, and Universiti Putra Malaysia. According to the data, there is little cooperation among authors, colleges, and nations tackling urban poverty. Malaysian research and contributions to the study of urban poverty are weak.</p>

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INTRODUCTION

Global urbanization is a growing phenomenon. Urban regions are where 55% of the world's population currently resides, and 70% of it is predicted to do so by 2050. Urban areas have more prospects for employment, higher social and economic growth, and better access to basic services than rural places. However, poverty is also more prevalent in metropolitan areas. The urban poor frequently have restricted access to essential services, employment prospects, and opportunities for social development in addition to not having enough income and resources to ensure a sufficient standard of living. Prior studies have noted rising urban poverty trends, which are partly attributable to the quickening urbanization processes in low- and middle-income countries. It is predicted that by 2035, the majority of people living in extreme poverty (i.e., with a daily income of less than US\$1.25) will reside in urban areas (Villar-Compte, et.al, 2021).

The "urbanization of poverty" has become a topic of increasing controversy during the past 20 years. The first dissection of the global dollar-a-day poverty estimates by rural and urban areas was done by Ravallion, Chen, and Sangraula (2008). They emphasized that while urbanization helps to reduce overall poverty, the proportion of the population living in poverty in cities is increasing. Additionally, according to UN-Habitat, the only source of globally comparable data on slum dwellers, 881 million people, or 30% of urban populations in developing countries, currently reside in slums. By 2050, however, this number could rise to 3 billion, or 60% of urban populations worldwide (Lucci, et.al, 2018).

All nations struggle with the socioeconomic issue of urban poverty. It attacked major nations like the United States and Japan in addition to poorer nations like Bangladesh, India, and Nepal. Even though it has been a focus of development initiatives since the end of the colonial era between the 1940s and 1950s, the issue of urban poverty has been the main focus in development initiatives or policies for some countries in the Asia and Pacific region, especially in developing countries like China, India, and Indonesia. Various agendas have been introduced and agreed upon to overcome it (Abdul Rahman, et.al, 2020).

According to Mathur (2013), urban poverty, in contrast to rural poverty, is complicated and multi-dimensional, going beyond a lack of money or consumption. Its numerous characteristics connect to the vulnerable state of the poor due to their lack of access to land and housing, physical and mental health, and other necessities. Infrastructure and services, sources of income and employment, institutions for health and education, social security networks, and voice and empowerment are the three categories. Urbanization has been accompanied in the majority of developing Asia by slums, a lack of housing, informality, deteriorating living circumstances, rising threats from climate change, and exclusive urban forms. According to UN-Habitat, 60% of the world's slum dwellers are in Asia, and many more people reside in slum-like circumstances in places that are officially classified as non-slums. In Asian cities and towns, there is a high rate of working poor and informality.

Urban Poverty in Malaysia

The term "poverty" refers to the situation of shortage that people experience, which limits their opportunities for a more relaxed life. This level of poverty demonstrates how a person's lack of resources, particularly in terms of money and goods, contributes to their inability to continue living a more pleasant life. According to the country's poverty index, this poverty is also characterized as a failure to acquire a stable source of income. In addition, through the implementation of the New Economic Policy (NEP), Malaysia is not far behind in setting the national poverty index line as defined in the Plan 2nd Malaysia (RMK2) through international bilateral agreement. In addition, Line The Poverty Index (GIK), which is based on minimum expenses, is mentioned to necessities of life like food, shelter, clothing, health, and education. Furthermore, poverty comprises a number of elements that limit one's ability to improve their socioeconomic standing, including their residence, their ability to access basic necessities, their education, their ability to access wholesome food, and so forth (Zin & Tambi, 2018).

Infrastructure development has supported the economy's rapid growth, and cities in Malaysia are now the country's major concentrations of people. In Malaysia, metropolitan regions were home to about 78% of households in 2016, up from 69% in 2009. Due to the abundance of work prospects, self-improvement opportunities are a driving force behind the movement of rural populations to urban areas. Therefore, many

people move, either from rural areas or across international borders, in order to take advantage of assured increased economic, educational, and social prospects. Uncontrolled urbanization has produced a population that is unstable and endangers the quality of life for city dwellers. 39.6% of Malaysians residing in metropolitan areas only have education up to the Malaysian Certificate of Education (SPM) level, according to data from the Department of Statistics Malaysia for 2017. Environmental concerns can endanger the quality of living society while education in Malaysia's urban community is still at a low level (Hasfazli & Ramli, 2021).

Urban poverty is multi-dimensional; its dimensions relate to the various forms of deprivations, disadvantages, and risks, and are manifest in the lack of access of the poor in cities and towns to basic services such as water and sanitation, shelter, and livelihood, and as is becoming increasingly evident, to health, education, social security, and empowerment and voice (Mathur, 2013).

Initiatives and endeavors that utilized this multi-dimensional poverty idea were seen in the Malaysian setting in national strategic plans, such as the most recent 11th Malaysia Plan. Although the Malaysian government made a great effort, practical implementation of this idea is still in its early stages. As a result, the income-based poverty definition, which encompasses both absolute and relative poverty, has been used to quantify and understand the current state of poverty in Malaysia. The idea of poverty is at a turning point, and work must be done to fully understand it and contextualize it within the larger framework of development, which includes multi-dimensional methods rather than uni-dimensional ones. As evidenced by studies on urban development and urban poverty in Malaysia, it is time for scholars and policy-makers to revisit, redefine, and also reconceptualize the concept of poverty, since it is no longer just a problem that affects the whims of rural citizens. The situation is made more difficult in Malaysia in particular because the country's citizenry is made up of people of many different ethnic backgrounds, with Malays, Chinese, and Indians being the three most significant ethnic groups there. The Malaysian social structure's ethnic diversity will show how various sociocultural and economic contexts influence and define poverty (Leng, et.al, 2018).

Research Question

- What is the trend/What are the research trends in urban poverty studies according to the year of publication?
- What are the popular keywords related to the study?
- Who has been published in the area concerning the authors, their affiliated organizations, and countries?
- What is the co-authorship status?
- What is the co-citations status?

METHODOLOGY

According to Verbeek et. al, (2002), bibliometrics is the combination, management, and analysis of bibliographic data gleaned from publications with a scientific bent. In addition to general descriptive data like publishing journals, year of publication, and major author categorization, it also includes sophisticated approaches such as document co-citation analysis (Wu & Wu, 2017). For an efficient review of the literature, the creation of a bibliography, and the achievement of trustworthy results, respectively, a series of appropriate keywords, literature searches, and analyses are needed. Readers can get a comprehensive understanding of the research topic over time by using bibliometric analysis. We searched the Scopus database for pertinent studies.

Data search strategy

According to Sudakova, et.al, (2022), Scopus is a top-notch research platform that makes it possible to find, analyze, and share information in the humanities, social sciences, and natural sciences. The method for conducting research is made more productive and efficient by the Scopus database. The Scopus database was chosen since it contains information for bibliometric analysis and indexes the top journals in the field of education. We searched the Scopus database for pertinent studies. The most thorough search was conducted, and different terms were favored. On the website for the Scopus database, a search was conducted

online. The search terms "urban poverty", and "Malaysia" were chosen. Then, limitations like language were put in place. The last search term used was this one.

The search terms for article retrieval were determined by a study using a screening sequence. Urban AND poverty AND Malaysia AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR 2023)) were the search terms used to access the Scopus database and assemble 13,355 documents. Afterward, the final search string refinement included 5,419 research articles in English which were used for bibliometric analysis.

Data analysis

Data sets were obtained from the Scopus database covering the years 2019 to 2023 and were analyzed using the VOSviewer software version 1.6.15. The data sets contained the research publication year, publication title, author name, journal, citation, and keyword. By using the VOS clustering and mapping methods, this program was used for analysis and map creation. VOSViewer is a substitute for the Multidimensional Scaling (MDS) approach (Van Eck and Waltman, 2010), and it is similar to MDS in that it focuses on placing objects in low-dimensional spaces in such a way that the distance between any two objects accurately reflects how related and similar they are to one another (Appio et al., 2014).

After lowering the weighted sum of the squared distances between all item pairs, VOSviewer arranges objects in the shape of a map. Appio claims that the LinLog/modularity normalization was put into practice. Additionally, patterns based on mathematical correlations were discovered by applying visualization techniques through VOSviewer to the data set, and analyses such as keyword co-occurrence, citation analysis, and co-citation analysis were carried out (Appio et al., 2014).

RESEARCH FINDINGS

1. What are the trend/What are the research trends in urban poverty studies according to the year of publication?

5,419 document results	
Year ↓	Documents ↑
2023	788
2022	1707
2021	1217
2020	956
2019	751

Figure 1: Research trends in urban poverty studies

Figure 1 shows the number of urban poverty publications published each year between 2019 and 2023. The figure shows that research on urban poverty is insignificant and relatively unstable, ranging from 60 (2019) to 10 (2023). There were 751 publications published in 2019, representing 13.86%, 956 publications in 2020, representing 17.64%, 1217 publications in 2021, representing 22.46%, 1707 publications in 2022, representing 31.50%, and 788 publications in 2023, representing 14.54%.

2. What are the popular keywords related to the study and have they evolved/changed during the last five years?

Figure 2: Network visualization of co-occurrence

The largest cluster is the red cluster with 233 keywords. Words like sustainable development, economic development, financial development, poverty, urban planning, bibliometric, financial inclusion, social capital, higher education, entrepreneur, politics, cointegration, land use, remote sensing, and health risks, were the most used keywords. The green cluster is the second one with 78 keywords. These include female, young, adult, high school, education, mental health, depression, morbidity, quality of life, and residents are predominant. In the third cluster, the blue cluster with 64 keywords, human, mother, pregnancy, child, school child, preschool child, vegetable, infant, body weight, underweight, diet, and newborn is highlighted. And the

fourth-largest clusters the one in yellow, with 58 keywords, Malaysia, west Malaysia, health risk, awareness, food security, water, housing affordability, livestock, genetics, hygiene, infection risk, fish, cities, and water supply were the most used. In other clusters, the most popular keywords are health care cost, health services, motivation, household, family size, health care, utilization, health care personnel for the purple cluster (43 keywords); air pollution, crime, health hazard, parks, recreational, recreational park, vegetation for the turquoise cluster (6 keywords); tuberculosis in the orange cluster only 1 keyword). These findings highlight the impacts of urban poverty on the life condition of urban society.

3. Who and how much has been published in the area concerning the authors, their affiliated organizations, and countries?

Documents by author

Scopus

Compare the document counts for up to 15 authors.

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Figure 3: The authors who write the most cited articles

Table 1: List of authors who write the most cited articles

Authors	Number of cited articles
Zaman, K.	19
Godman, B.	17
Nassani, A.A.	15
Haque, M.	14
Anser, M.K.	13
Dong, K.	13
Gupta, R.	13
McKee, M.	13
Sadiq, M.	13
Bello, A.K.	12

Zaman, K. published 19 articles (13.38%), Godman, B. published 17 articles (11.97%), Nassani, A.A. published 15 articles (10.56%), Haque, M. published 14 articles (9.86%), Anser M.K., Dong, K., Gupta, R., McKee, M. and Sadiq, M. published 13 articles respectively (9.15%), Bello, A.K. published 12 articles (8.45%). (See Figure 3 and Table 1)

Documents by affiliation

Scopus

Compare the document counts for up to 15 affiliations.

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Figure 4: The affiliated organizations that published most articles

Table 2: List of affiliated organizations that published more articles

Affiliated organizations	Number of articles
Universiti Sains Malaysia	166
Universiti Malaya	165
Universiti Putra Malaysia	159
Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia	149
Universiti Teknologi MARA	90
Universiti Utara Malaysia	65
Universiti Teknologi Malaysia	62
Chinese Academy of Sciences	53
Taylor's University Malaysia	53
University of Johannesburg	46

Regarding the organizations, institutions or universities that provide great work on urban poverty, we have mainly “Universiti Sains Malaysia” with 166 publications, i.e. 16.47%, “Universiti Malaya” with 165 publications, i.e. 16.37%, “Universiti Putra Malaysia” with 159 publications, i.e. 15.77%, “Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia” with 149 publications, i.e. 14.78%, “Universiti Teknologi MARA” with 90 publications, i.e. 8.93%, “Universiti Utara Malaysia” with 65 publications, i.e. 6.45%, “Universiti Teknologi

Malaysia” with 62 publications, i.e. 6.15%, “Chinese Academy of Sciences and Taylor’s University Malaysia published 53 publications respectively, i.e. 5.26%, University of Johannesburg with 46 publications, i.e. 4.56% (see Figure 4 and Table 2).

Documents by country or territory

Scopus

Compare the document counts for up to 15 countries/territories.

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Figure 5: The countries that published most articles

Table 3: List of countries that published most articles

Countries	Number of articles
Malaysia	1217
China	1004
United States	693
United Kingdom	501
Australia	391
Indonesia	389
India	383
Pakistan	330
South Africa	278
Nigeria	232

By observing Figure 5 and Table 3, the country that published the most articles is Malaysia (1217 publications, 22.46%), followed by China (1004 publications, 18.53%), the United States (693 publications, 12.79%), the United Kingdom (501 publications, 9.25%), Australia (391 publications, 7.22%), Indonesia (389 publications, 7.18%), India (383 publications, 7.07%), Pakistan (330 publications, 6.09%), South Africa (278 publications, 5.13%) and Nigeria (232 publications, 4.28%) (see Figure 5 and Table 3).

4. What is the co-authorships status?

Figure 6: Network visualization of co-authorship

As shown in Figure 6, the analysis revealed that the relevant cooperative author groups, which are the subject of urban poverty research, are displayed in various colors. The largest group is the red cluster composed of 14 authors, among which authors with more publications are Liu Y. (16 publications), Zhang, H. (10 publications), and Chen, X., Zhang, X. and Li, Z. (9 publications respectively). The second group is the green one, composed of 10 authors. The most prominent in this group are Wang, J. (18 publications), Wang, Y. (15 publications), and Zhao. J. and Khan, M.A. (9 publications respectively). The third-largest group is one in blue. In this group of 9 authors, Li, Y. stands out with 14 publications, Liu, X. and Li, H. (12 publications respectively) and Li, B. (7 publications).

5. What is the co-citations status?

Figure 7: Network visualization of co-citation

Figure 7 shows that the largest cluster is the red cluster. The most prominent in this group are Wang, Y. (690 citations), followed by Zhang, Y. (671 citations), and Liu, Y. (640 citations). The second-largest group is the one in green. The authors that have the most citation are Shahbaz, M. (629 citations), Ahmad, M. (451 citations), and Khan, I. (416 citations). The third group is the blue one which has 88 authors. In this group, Sadiq, M. has 381 citations, then Irfan, M. has 290 citations and Mohsin, M. has 276 citations.

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSION

We analyzed 5,419 research articles on urban poverty in Malaysia published between 2019 and 2023, which represents 40.58% of the 13,355 total research articles published in Scopus. To initially identify the production by years, universities, nations, authors, and citations, we quantitatively analyzed the metadata.

2022 is the year in which the most articles on urban poverty are published, which is as many as 1707 articles in 5 years between 2019 and 2020. Other than that, the co-occurrence analysis revealed that when searching for related keywords in urban poverty publications between 2019 and 2023, we got very few hits, example "sustainable development" (178 occurrences), "economic development" (113 occurrences) "poverty" (111 occurrences) "urban planning (27 occurrences), "financial inclusion" (23 occurrences). These results demonstrate the paucity of contemporary research on urban poverty.

Regarding the authors, Zaman, K., Godman, B. and Nassani, A.A are the authors who have published the most articles in the field. Unfortunately, they are not the most cited; among those most cited, we have Wang, Y., followed by Zhang, Y. and Liu, Y. The authors that has the most co-authorship are Liu, Y., Zhang, H., and Chen, X. The most significant organization in the subject is not determined by the number of publications from one nation, institution, or author. The quality of the work, especially the community that can read and evaluate the work, is more important for being a reference in a study field than the quantity. To submit your work, you must therefore locate a journal that is respected in the industry.

"Universiti Sains Malaysia", "Universiti Malaya" and "Universiti Putra Malaysia" are institutions that provide great work on urban poverty. These universities are located in the city center which allows them to be

exposed to urban poverty. Because of that, Malaysia is one of the countries that publishes the most articles on this topic compared to China, the United States, and the United Kingdom.

There are some limitations in this study. Firstly, not all academic publications, like WoS, were included in the data collection because we solely used Scopus. Furthermore, while terms like "urban city," "urban ghetto," and others might be used to broaden the search scope, we only utilized the term "urban poverty" as a search term in the data search. We also searched articles related to Malaysia only and others might be searched Asian countries or worldwide. The results demonstrated that our dataset, which was gathered from Scopus, is acceptable because it covers all key features of urban poverty, despite the possibility that using synonymous search terms could produce a dataset that is more accurate on the issue. It is recommended for future studies to focus on rural poverty and the well-being of the B40 group in Malaysia.

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